

THE EXPRESSION OF MAGIC REALISM IN ANGELA CARTER'S
NOVEL "NIGHTS AT THE CIRCUS"

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Abstract: The concept of "magic realism" refers to a literary style that seamlessly incorporates magical or supernatural events into a realistic narrative, questioning the nature of reality and emphasizing the creative process through a blend of fact and fantasy. Originating with Latin American writers in the 1940s, this style integrates cultural, folkloric, and geographical elements to depict complex realities. Angela Carter, a prominent 20th-century magic-realist writer, exemplifies this style in her novel "Nights at the Circus" (1984). Set against a backdrop of post-imperialist Britain, the novel intertwines fantastical and political themes, exploring identity, feminism, and societal transformation. Carter uses magical realism to critique and transcend conventional boundaries, creating a narrative that is both enchanting and thought-provoking.

The methods and findings highlight how magic realism operates as a metafictional tool, providing commentary on literature, society, and politics. By merging the magical with the real, Carter and other writers in this genre challenge traditional realism and invite readers to explore multiple realities. The historical development of magic realism, from its roots in German art criticism to its popularization by Latin American writers like Gabriel García Márquez, underscores its evolution and the debates surrounding its definition. Critics and authors alike grapple with its effectiveness and limitations, emphasizing its role in bridging ideal and achievable realities. Through vivid portrayals of social class and time manipulation, Carter's narrative underscores

the fluidity of identity and the entrenched inequalities within societal structures. Ultimately, "Nights at the Circus" offers a rich exploration of reality, perception, and the power of imagination.

Key words: Magic Realism, Angela Carter, Nights at the Circus, Franz Roh, latin american writing, surrealism, postmodernism, Gabriel García Márquez, One Hundred Years of Solitude, social class, time, identity, feminism, metafiction, storytelling, reality and myth, culture, book review, history, European art.

Introduction

The term 'magic realism' is extensively refers to the style of writing or technique which includes magical as well as supernatural events narrated realistically without any doubt about improbability of the events. It questions the nature of reality and draws attention to the act of creation by using a new combination of fact and fancy. The term 'magical realism' (Magischer Realismus) had its first use in 1925 in German art critic Franz Roh's attempt to define a return to a more realistic style after the abstraction of Expressionism.[1] This movement began with Latin American writers portraying reality with surreal and magical elements to show that their culture was dynamic and complex. Its origins are said to date back to the 1940s, when Spanish-American writers such as Miguel Ángel Asturias and Alejo Carpentier wrote the seminal novels *The Corn People* and *The Realm of This World*, respectively. These writers drew inspiration from various aspects of indigenous peoples, including folklore, cultural beliefs, and features of the geographic and political landscape.

One of the 20th century's most innovative , most famous magic-realist writers and fashionable authors of English literature was thought to be Angela Carter as .She was raised in a calm, middle-class home in a London suburb after her birth in 1940. She lived in Japan for three years (1969–1972), during which time she developed an interest in Japanese surrealism. At a young age, she secured her first job as a reporter. Her "demonic inaccuracy as regards fact," however, did not impede her career.[2] Angela Carter's "Nights at the Circus" intricately intertwines the fantastical with the political,

offering a captivating narrative that delves into themes of identity, feminism, and societal transformation. Published in 1984, the novel reflects Carter's own experiences and perspectives, shaped by the backdrop of a declining, post-imperialist Britain. In essence, Carter's incorporation of magical realism serves as a means to critique and transcend conventional boundaries, offering readers a rich and multi-layered exploration of reality and imagination. Through her unique blend of the real and the unreal, she creates a literary landscape that is both enchanting and thought-provoking.

Findings and methods:

“Poets and beggars, musicians and prophets, warriors and scoundrels, all creatures of that unbridled reality, we have had to ask but little of imagination, for our crucial problem has been a lack of conventional means to render our lives believable. This, my friends, is the crux of our solitude” (“Gabriel García Márquez—Nobel Lecture”).

These are the words of the much beloved author Gabriel García Márquez in his Nobel Prize lecture titled “The Solitude of Latin America.” His novel *One Hundred Years of Solitude* (1967) was so influential that some of the world's best novelists copy his work to this day. But Gabriel García Márquez is also famous for another reason: he was one of the forerunners of magical realism and the first to popularize it in the global consciousness. Whether magical realism is a trend isolated to Latin America (as many critics suggest) or an entirely new style, *One Hundred Years of Solitude* is widely regarded as the premiere novel of magical realism. But Gabriel García Márquez insisted that he was simply trying to write about reality as he knew it..

The term "magical realism" has been used rather indiscriminately in the literary world since its introduction in the world of surrealist art and after the use of it by the Latin American writer Jorge Luis Borges. It is derived from a combination of terms often applied to supernatural or mythological literature from the turbulent countries of Latin America. University professors use the term to describe works of literature, critics apply it to many works, and young fantasy writers often classify their works under the category of "magical realism". But what is magical realism? Is it a genre?

Style? A trend that's going away soon? Beginning with the late Gabriel García Márquez's seminal novel *One Hundred Years of Solitude*, "surrealism," originally limited to the art of Salvador Dalí, suddenly became the magical realism of "surrealism" and applied to almost any literary experience involving the supernatural. Confused with Reality Critics have attempted to define magical realism in order to establish it as a genre, but have often failed miserably by failing to identify specific reasons why magical realism was written.

"Magic realism" was first coined by the German art critic Franz Roh in his work *Nach-Expressionismus, Magischer Realismus: Probleme der neuesten Europäischen Malerei* (Post-Expressionism, Magic Realism: Problems of the Newest European Painting). In this work, Roh applies magic realism to the realm of European pictorial art of the interwar years and to artists such as Otto Dix, Carl Grossberg, George Grosz, Christian Schad, Georg Schrimpf, Franz Radziwill and Adolf Ziegler. For critics such as Seymour Menton, the 1925 publication of Roh's book serves to position magic realism in relation to a specific geographical, political and historical context. According to Menton, Roh's study reveals a post-war 'search for an alternative to the limitations of an overly rational and technological society.[3] Magic realism, for Menton, represents a European response to the horror of the world's first truly industrial war, and a specifically German response to the bitterness of defeat and the enormous political, social and economic turmoil resulting from the conditions of surrender.

'Between the "real" and the "magic" there is a third category of reality. It consists of a fusion of the visible and the tangible, of hallucinations and fantasy. It is similar to what the Surrealists around Breton wished for, and it is what can be called "magic realism". This magic realism, of course, has a direct relation with the original mentality of the Indians. The Indian thinks in images; he sees things not so much as phenomena in themselves but as translated into other dimensions, dimensions in which reality disappears and dreams appear and are transformed into visible and concrete forms.[4]

Magical realism both informs the prevailing postmodern attitude toward reality (there is not just one reality, but a kaleidoscope of realities) and constitutes at the same time the most successful medium for its signification—hence my adherence to Theo D'haen's statement, "The cutting edge of postmodernism is magic realism". In the vein of most postmodernist fiction, magical realist writing is metafictional: "the texts provide commentaries on themselves, often complete with occasional mises-en-abyme—those miniature emblematic textual self-portraits". Moreover, and this would be another postmodernist trait of magical realism, the texts comment not only on themselves, but also on literature at large (through frequent intertextual elements), on the social establishment, and on the political canon. Many magical realist authors, such as Kundera and Rushdie, for instance, create what Faris calls a "poetics of subversion, of the non-cooptability of people, events, laughter, love, objects, even images". As a poetics of subversion, the linguistic strategies of magical realism undermine the canon from the inside, masquerading normality in a paranormal context—very much in the manner of a carnivalistic ritual.[5]

"Nights at the Circus" stands as Angela Carter's acclaimed masterpiece, weaving a tale around the enigmatic winged heroine, Fevvers, whose journey is as bizarre as it is adventurous. Set across various locales including a whorehouse, a museum of female monsters, the circus, and even a prison, the novel unfolds through the lens of a classic three-act play structure, with Carter's signature flair for the fantastical. Divided into parts titled London, Petersburg, and Siberia, the narrative kicks off in 1899, a time Carter describes as the "fag-end" of the nineteenth century. Angela Carter believes that the key obstacle preventing people from enjoying true freedom is their limited imagination. In her stories, she dismantles the borders of logical, static life, allowing for an abundance of inexhaustible beauty in the realm of imagination. She is not comfortable with social identities given to people and "her sustaining goal is the explosion of the doxa by which so many lives are routinely shaped and in the name of

which human beings so often consent to while their days away in ponderous thoughtlessness”.[6]

The novel begins with Jack Walser, an ambitious American journalist, seeking to unravel the truth behind Fevvers' mythical origins. As he conducts an interview with the winged woman, hoping to debunk her fantastical tale, Fevvers takes charge of the conversation from the outset. Set in Fevvers' opulently squalid changing room after a circus performance, the first act thrusts readers into the heart of the story without preamble. Fevvers, far from passively responding to Walser's inquiries, commandeers the dialogue, challenging traditional power dynamics with her irreverent and assertive demeanor. Her account of being 'hatched' rather than born, delivered with theatrical flair and unapologetic confidence, sets the stage for a narrative that defies conventions and embraces the carnivalesque spirit of subversion.

Further underscoring this theme are the clowns, whose jovial facade masks inner turmoil and mistreatment, serving as a poignant illustration of the disparity between appearance and truth. Even the animals within the circus defy categorization, possessing magical qualities that transcend conventional understanding. Through these fantastical elements, Carter invites readers to reassess their perceptions of reality, challenging conventional norms and prompting deeper reflection on the nature of truth and appearance in the narrative landscape. Ultimately, their reunion symbolizes the integration of the New Man and New Woman, heralding a future wherein gender hierarchies are dismantled, and women emancipated from their subservient roles. This denouement serves as a harbinger of a more egalitarian society, wherein women are no longer relegated to the status of mere possessions, and men relinquish their claims to superiority. Thus, the narrative culminates in a hopeful vision of progress and equality, poised at the dawn of the new century.

Throughout the narrative, the dichotomy between appearance and reality permeates the fabric of the story, posing a central dilemma for characters and readers alike. At the heart of this theme lies the enigma surrounding Fevvers' wings, which

defy conventional understanding. Despite her outwardly human appearance, Fevvers lays claim to ancestral wings, blurring the boundaries between reality and myth. Likewise, the women inhabiting the brothel challenge preconceived notions, presenting themselves as self-sufficient individuals akin to suffragists, contrary to societal expectations.

Social class indeed emerges as a salient thematic concern within "Nights at the Circus," permeating the narrative fabric and shaping the trajectories of its characters. Fevvers' strategic manipulation of her backstory to align with notions of aristocracy underscores the enduring significance of social status and the lengths to which individuals will go to attain acceptance within higher echelons of society. The hierarchical structure within the circus serves as a microcosm reflecting broader societal stratification, with Fevvers occupying the apex of the class pyramid while the clowns languish at its nadir, relegated to a position of inferiority within the troupe's social hierarchy.

Results and Discussions:

Magic realist writing is characterized by its metafictional nature and its ability to comment on the text itself, literature, social norms, and political ideologies. It presents a linguistic spectacle that aims to blur the lines between words and the world, creating a reality that is both unreal yet true. The text also touches upon the historical development of magic realism, tracing its roots back to the concept of the marvelous reality and surrealism. It discusses the challenges of defining magic realism and the literary boundaries it pushes against, echoing the struggles of signification and representation within the genre. The narrative highlights the tension between magic and realism and how magic realism offers a way to transcend the limitations of traditional realism. By incorporating magical elements, magical realist texts attempt to bridge the gap between the ideal and the achievable. The discussion also includes the reaction of critics, artists, and the public to magic realism, contrasting it with surrealism and abstract expressionism. The text poses questions about the effectiveness and limitations

of magic realism in conveying meaning and creating a unified imaginary world for readers to explore and interpret.

Even the term "magic realism" has engendered disagreement since Franz Roh introduced it into artistic discourse in the mid-1920s through the German phrase *Magischer Realismus*, a "counter-movement" in art through which "the charm of the object was rediscovered." When his *Nach-Expressionismus (Magischer Realismus): Probleme der neuesten Europaischen Malerei*, published in German in 1925, was translated and disseminated in Spanish through the *Revista de Occidente* two years later, his articulation of this new sensibility in art doubtlessly had a strong influence on Latin American writers searching for a suitable means to express the "marvelous reality" unique to their own culture. In *German Art in the 20th Century*, Roh later schematized the differences between expressionism and post-expressionism (which he associates with magic realism), but his focus upon the visual arts reduces the usefulness of his charted oppositions in a literary context.[7] Faris describes this verbal magic as a "closing of the gap between words and world, or a demonstration of what we might call the linguistic nature of experience. This magic happens when a metaphor is made real". In other words, when a metaphor is made real, signification seems to circumvent the signified (the concept): the signifier (the word) creates a reality (a referent) experience-able as such within the text only. The phenomenon of verbal magic, or the literalization of the metaphor, makes sense especially in the concrete case of an artistic shock chronotope: the violent time-space, which could not be conceptualized because of its traumatizing effect, is recreated, or re-presented, in the text and thus rendered directly accessible to the readers' experience as felt reality-unreal but true.[8]

Carter adeptly illuminates the stark disparities in living conditions and social standing through vivid descriptions of the clowns' impoverished existence, thereby underscoring the pervasive influence of class dynamics within the circus milieu. Walser's descent from a position of societal privilege to that of a lowly clown further underscores the fluid and often capricious nature of social mobility, highlighting the

tenuousness of social standing and the precariousness of identity within a stratified society. Through these nuanced portrayals, Carter invites readers to contemplate the entrenched inequalities inherent in social class structures and the profound implications they hold for individual agency and self-perception.

Time emerges as a central theme in the narrative, permeating both the storyline and the novel's magical elements. The manipulation of time is exemplified by Ma Nelson's broken clock, which perpetually indicates midnight in the darkened confines of the brothel.

This suspension of time creates a disorienting atmosphere, blurring the boundaries between past, present, and future. With Ma Nelson's passing, Fevvers inherits the broken clock, symbolizing her newfound control over time.

Throughout the narrative, the concept of time remains elusive and fluid, further underscored by instances such as Walser's perplexing encounter with the striking of the Big Ben clock. His disconcerting experience, wherein the clock strikes midnight multiple times in quick succession, highlights the malleability of time within the novel's universe. This ambiguity is compounded by Fevvers and Lizzie's revelation in the *Envoi*, wherein they disclose their deliberate manipulation of Walser's perception of time using Ma Nelson's clock.

In this way, time serves as a multifaceted thematic element, imbued with both symbolic significance and narrative intrigue. Its manipulation reflects the characters' agency and underscores the novel's exploration of reality, perception, and the fluidity of existence. As the narrative unfolds, time emerges as a dynamic force, shaping the characters' experiences and challenging conventional notions of temporal order and progression.

Conclusion:

Magic realism, emerging from European art criticism and flourishing in Latin American literature, offers a unique approach to storytelling that challenges conventional narratives. Writers like Gabriel García Márquez and Angela Carter have

adeptly used the genre to blend the magical with the real, inviting readers to explore themes of identity, feminism, and societal transformation.

Through works like "One Hundred Years of Solitude" and "Nights at the Circus," magic realism provides a platform for reflecting on the complexities of human experience. By seamlessly integrating the fantastical into everyday life, these writers create narratives that defy categorization and provoke critical reflection.

Magic realism operates as a form of metafiction, providing commentary on literature, society, and the nature of storytelling itself. By blurring the boundaries between reality and myth, magic realist texts challenge readers to reassess their understanding of the world around them.

Ultimately, magic realism celebrates the richness and diversity of human experience, offering a space for imaginative exploration and critical reflection. As writers continue to experiment with its possibilities, the genre remains a vibrant and dynamic form of storytelling that sparks imaginative journeys into uncharted realms.

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